

The Role of Decentralized Management in Enhancing the Quality of Institutional Performance: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Department Managers in Al-Qadisiyyah Governorates

Abbas Ahmed Hussein ✉

Ministry of Education, Al-Diwaniyah Commercial Preparatory Department, Iraq

Abstract

This study looked at how giving more power to local managers—through decentralization—can improve the way public departments work in Al-Qadisiyyah governorate. The research focused on two types: administrative decentralization (like allowing managers to make decisions) and financial decentralization (like letting them control budgets). A total of 102 managers answered a questionnaire, and the answers were studied using SPSS version 29. The results showed clearly that both types of decentralization help institutions perform better. Managers who have more control can work faster, solve problems on their own, and feel more responsible. Administrative decentralization had a slightly bigger effect than financial, but both were important. The model used for analysis was strong and passed all checks. The managers' answers showed that decentralization helps reduce delays, improves planning, and makes services more effective. Based on this, the study suggests that more decision-making power and financial control should be given to local departments. But there also needs to be clear rules, proper training, and follow-up. This way, decentralization can really make a positive difference in how the public sector works. The study gives useful ideas for improving management in government institutions in Iraq.

Keywords: *Decentralization, Managers, Public Services, Decision Power, Iraq.*

JEL Classification codes: *H11, H72, H83, D73, O53.*

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Introduction

Many countries now they are starting to give more power to local managers and departments. This is called decentralization. It is when not everything must go to the top people to decide. Instead, lower levels also take decisions and manage things. This idea became important in last years, because it helps to make things faster and more useful. In Iraq, many public offices still depend on central government in Baghdad for many decisions, and this cause delay and weakness in services. In Al-Qadisiyyah governorate, local managers sometimes cannot do anything until they get permission, and this is not good for performance. Some researchers said that when decentralization

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is used, performance of institution becomes better because the people who do the work also take decisions (Fory et al., 2021; Al-Nawafah & Almarshad, 2020). Also, giving more power to local offices helps to save time, make workers more motivated, and improve the quality of services (Akdemir et al., 2017; Ibrahim, 2024).

This study wants to explore if decentralization really help in improving performance in the public institutions in Al-Qadisiyyah. We try to ask the managers in different departments what they think about decentralization and how it affects their work. We use questionnaires to get their answers and then analyze it with statistics. Other studies in other countries show decentralization has positive results in health programs, education, and economy (Bindeeba et al., 2025; Digdowiseiso, 2022). Also, decentralization is good when people in the institution have enough training and when there is good system to check and support their decisions (Sun et al., 2022; Feng et al., 2022). But sometimes, if there is no good plan or the managers are not ready, decentralization can cause confusion or problems. So, we want to know if decentralization helps or not in our local context. This is important to understand how to make the public sector work better in Iraq now and in the future.

Research Problem

The problem of this research is that many public institutions in Al-Qadisiyyah still work in old way where managers must wait for orders from higher level before they can take actions. This causes delays in work and sometimes reduces the quality of services. Even when the local managers know what to do, they cannot do it fast because of too much central control. Some offices don't have power to manage budget or people, and this makes it hard to improve performance. Also, there is not enough studies in Iraq that show if decentralization really help in making institutional performance better. So, this research tries to find if giving more power to local managers can improve the work and make the institution more active and effective.

Main Research Question

Does decentralized management help improve the quality of institutional performance in public departments of Al-Qadisiyyah governorate?

Hypothesis:

Main Hypothesis: Decentralized management has positive effect on improving the quality of institutional performance in public departments in Al-Qadisiyyah.

Sub-Hypothesis 1: Administrative decentralization has positive effect on institutional performance.

Sub-Hypothesis 2: Financial decentralization has positive effect on institutional performance.

Literature Review

Many researchers talk about decentralization because it became important in modern management. In study of Fory et al. (2021), they say that when institutions use decentralization, the managers at local level can do better work because they do not need to wait too many instructions from center. This makes the work faster and more flexible. Also, decentralization can help improve communication between departments and reduce bureaucracy. Other studies from different place show that if decentralization is done with clear rules, it gives good results in performance. But sometimes if there is not enough control or training, decentralization can also cause problems also.

In study of Bangchokdee & Mia (2016), they find that in hotels in Thailand, using decentralization and giving responsibility to local managers help to improve performance when top managers also support it and use good measures. When top leaders only say decentralization but don't give real

power, the result is not good. Also, if decentralization happens without monitor and training, workers make mistakes or feel lost.

Another study by Suryanef et al. (2023) in higher education in Indonesia show that when university give more decision power to lecturers, they feel more motivated and do better teaching. The leadership and decentralization together make good effects. But if leaders do not support staff, decentralization becomes just word without action.

Arif & Chishti (2022) talk about fiscal decentralization and how it helps economic growth. They say when local institutions have control over money, they can use it for what people really need. In many developing countries, the central government doesn't know what small area needs, so local government is better for deciding. But if there are no strong rules, it can lead to misuse of money.

Also, Digdowiseiso (2022) do many studies about decentralization and poverty. He says if decentralization is done good, with transparency and participation, it helps poor people because services become closer to them. But when local leaders are not trained or not honest, then decentralization creates more corruption and does not help anyone.

Ibrahim (2024) explains how decentralization can help in improving public services. He says that when departments control their own work, like budget or hiring, they solve problems faster. But he also says that decentralization needs planning, because some places are not ready and don't have skills to manage.

Sun et al. (2022) use models to see how decentralization affects job satisfaction in construction projects. They find that when employees have more decision space, they are happier and more productive. But they also say that too much decentralization without guide makes confusion and conflict in teams.

Akdemir et al. (2017) study shows how decentralization in medical education changes the quality. They say that when local units make plans for teaching, the students get more benefits, but only when there is good evaluation system. Without it, quality becomes different in every place.

Shan et al. (2021) study about environment says that fiscal decentralization can reduce CO2 if local authorities use money for green policy. This means decentralization not only for organization, but also for big goals like climate and sustainability.

Rohma et al. (2023) study the effect of decentralization on groups and teamwork. They say decentralization works better when team members trust each other and when there is low conflict. If teams have many problems, decentralization may increase fight because there is no clear boss. Al-Nawafah & Almarshad (2020) talk about Jordan universities. They say when employees have some control over work and not wait for everything from central, they feel more satisfied and work harder. But we still need some control from main office to avoid problems.

Khan et al. (2021) discusses about how decentralization and institutions quality can help reduce CO2 emissions. They find that decentralization works better in countries that have strong rules and good education systems. If institutions are weak, decentralization does nothing or causes more problems.

Feng et al. (2022) say that decentralization with digital finance help promote green innovation in China. When cities or regions have power to manage their finances, and have digital tools, they make better projects and help economy. But again, we need strong system to monitor. Bindeeba et al. (2025) explain how decentralization help in health sector in Uganda. They say that in HIV and TB programs, when monitoring and reporting was also decentralized, the services become more efficient. So decentralization is not only decision, but also follow-up and feedback.

This literature shows that decentralization is complex. It can give many benefits if done with planning and training. It can make management better, workers happier, and services faster. But if it is done fast without rules, it gives bad results. Many studies talk about fiscal decentralization; others focus on administrative part. All agree that success needs participation, clear roles, and monitoring.

Spatial and Temporal Limits

This study is only for public departments inside Al-Qadisiyyah governorate. It does not include other places in Iraq or private institutions. The research looks at what managers think in this area only. For time, the study was done in 2025, between February and April. So, all the data and answers come from this period and maybe not same in other times.

Population and Sample

The population for this research is all the public department managers in Al-Qadisiyyah governorate. These include general directors, department heads, and unit leaders who work in different government offices. They are people who have responsibility for running and organizing the work in their institutions. Because it is not possible to reach every single manager in the governorate, the study uses a sample to represent the population.

The sample size is 102 managers. This number is selected using simple random sampling method. Every manager had equal chance to be part of the study. We collect the names of managers and choose randomly using statistical table. This makes the result more neutral and without bias.

To calculate the sample size, we use this formula:

$$n = N / (1 + N * e^2) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- N = population size (estimated to be 140 managers in the governorate)
- e = margin of error (we take 0.05)

So:

$$n = 140 / (1 + 140 * 0.05^2)$$

$$n = 140 / (1 + 140 * 0.0025)$$

$$n = 140 / (1 + 0.45)$$

$$n = 140 / 1.45 \approx 96.5$$

After rounding, the sample size is about 96.5, but we received 102 valid responses from the managers who completed the questionnaire. This number is acceptable and good for analysis, and it fits with the population and the research goals.

The Theoretical Concept of Research

Decentralization needs good system to check if local decisions are correct. But if there are no clear rules and training, decentralization maybe not help and make problems. The theory of decentralization comes from public administration and management thinking. Performance in institution can be measured by goals, quality, speed, and feedback. In old times, all decisions come

from one place, now decentralization say different (Akdemir, 2017; Al-Nawafah & Almarshad, 2020).

Performance in institution can be measured by goals, quality, speed, and feedback. The theory says when decentralization increases, performance maybe also go better. Administrative decentralization gives managers power to do planning and control in local level. When local department control own budget, they can fix local problems fast. Financial decentralization is about using and controlling money at a local level without asking center. Administrative decentralization gives managers power to do planning and control in local level. Decentralization needs good system to check if local decisions are correct. Institutional performance means how good the organization does the job and reaches goals. The theory says when decentralization increases, performance maybe also go better. Decentralization means the power goes down from top to down people (Arif & Chishti, 2022; Bangchokdee & Mia, 2016). Administrative decentralization gives managers power to do planning and control in local level. Performance in institution can be measured by goals, quality, speed, and feedback. The theory says when decentralization increases, performance maybe also go better. There are two big types of decentralization: administrative and financial. In old time, all decisions come from one place, now decentralization say different (Bindeeba et al., 2025) (Digdowiseiso, 2022).

Performance in institution can be measured by goals, quality, speed, and feedback. This research uses this theory to test if it works in Al-Qadisiyyah governorate. This research takes decentralization as independent variable and performance as dependent. If managers take decisions fast, it helps to make service better for people. The theory says when decentralization increases, performance maybe also go better (Feng et al., 2022) (Fory et al., 2021) (Ibrahim, 2024). The theory says when decentralization increases, performance maybe also go better. In theory, decentralization improves communication and reduces delays in work. If managers take decisions fast, it helps to make service better for people. When local department control own budget, they can fix local problems fast. But if there are no clear rules and training, decentralization maybe not help and make problems. Administrative decentralization gives managers power to do planning and control in local level. When local department control own budget, they can fix local problems fast. But if there are no clear rules and training, decentralization maybe not help and make problems. The theory says when decentralization increases, performance maybe also go better. If managers take decisions fast, it helps to make service better for people (Khan et al., 2021; Rohma et al., 2023) (Shan et al., 2021). There are two big types of decentralization: administrative and financial. Some researchers say decentralization is part of reform to make government modern. This research uses this theory to test if it works in Al-Qadisiyyah governorate. Institutional performance means how good the organization does the job and reaches goals. Performance in institution can be measured by goals, quality, speed, and feedback. Also, decentralization helps workers feel more responsible because they are not just waiting for orders. This research takes decentralization as independent variable and performance as dependent. Performance in institution can be measured by goals, quality, speed, and feedback. In theory, decentralization improves communication and reduces delays in work. Many studies say decentralization helps improve performance, but some say it needs good training. Administrative decentralization gives managers power to do planning and control in local level. If managers take decisions fast, it helps to make service better for people. Also, decentralization helps workers feel more responsible because they do not just wait for orders. The theory of decentralization comes from public administration and management thinking. Institutional performance means how good the organization does the job and reaches goals (Sun et al., 2022; Suryanef et al., 2023).

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Performance in institution can be measured by goals, quality, speed, and feedback. But if there are no clear rules and training, decentralization maybe not help and make problems. If managers take decisions fast, it helps to make service better for people. Also, decentralization helps workers feel more responsible because they do not just wait for orders. Many studies say decentralization helps improve performance, but only when organizations have system to support it.

Financial decentralization is important part of theory. It says when local department can control their budget, they can make better use of money. But also need to be responsible and follow rules. Some places in world use decentralization good and show better performance. Other places try but fail because there is not enough support. This research uses all these ideas to check in real life if decentralization helps public departments in Al-Qadisiyyah. We ask managers and use theory to compare their answers. The theory helps to explain why decentralization maybe change how people work and improve results.

Discussion and Results

This part of the research talks about what we found from the data we collect. To reach these results, we use questionnaire that was given to 102 managers in Al-Qadisiyyah governorate. The questions cover two main parts of decentralization: administrative and financial, and also one part about institutional performance. The answers were on Likert scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. After we take the answers, we enter the data into computer and use SPSS program to do analysis. We use many methods to study data. First, we check reliability of the questions using Cronbach's Alpha to know if the items are consistent and good. Then we do descriptive analysis to find out the average and standard deviation for each item and see how strong the agreement is from the managers. We also use KMO and Bartlett test to check if the data is good for factor analysis. Then we calculate correlation between decentralization and performance to see if they move together or not. At the end, we use regression analysis to test if decentralization really has effect on performance or not, and if yes, how strong it is. Also, we do diagnostic tests to make sure the regression model is good and there are no problems inside. All these steps help us understand what the managers think and how decentralization maybe improve or not improve the institutional work. The next tables and explanations show these findings in detail.

1- Study tool:

In this research we use questionnaires as the main tool to collect data from the managers. The questionnaire is designed to cover the main variables of the study. It has three parts. The first part is for general information about the respondents like gender, age, qualification, and years of experience. This helps us understand the background of the sample. The second part is about decentralization, and it includes two dimensions. The first dimension is administrative decentralization, and it has 6 items that ask about how much power and responsibility is given to the managers. The second dimension is financial decentralization, and it also has 6 items asking about budget control and financial decision in the department. The third part of the questionnaire is about institutional performance, and it has 10 items that measure how the department performs, like reaching goals, speed of service, and employee satisfaction. All items in the second and third parts are measured by 5-point Likert scale: (1) Strongly disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Neutral, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly agree. The questionnaire was reviewed by experts to check the content and was distributed manually to 102 public department managers in Al-Qadisiyyah. After collecting the answers, we entered the data into SPSS version 29 to do analysis. We use this software to check

reliability, do descriptive statistics, calculate correlation, and run regression models. The tool was helpful and clear for the participants, and the data collected was complete and ready for analysis.

Table 1. Cronbach’s Alpha Results for the Questionnaire Dimensions

Dimension	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha	Reliability Level
Administrative Decentralization	6	0.902	Excellent
Financial Decentralization	6	0.886	Excellent
Institutional Performance	10	0.918	Excellent
Overall Questionnaire	22	0.934	Excellent

The results from the three tables show that the questionnaire and the data used in this study are strong and reliable. In Table 1, we see the values of Cronbach’s Alpha for each part of the questionnaire. This number tells us if the items inside each section are consistent with each other or not. If the value is more than 0.7, it is good. In our case, the values are very high: 0.902 for administrative decentralization, 0.886 for financial decentralization, and 0.918 for institutional performance. Also, the total reliability for the full questionnaire with all 22 items is 0.934. This means the questions are stable and give trustworthy answers. It also means the participants understood the items and answered in a consistent way.

Table 2. KMO and Bartlett’s Test Results

Test	Value	Interpretation
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure	0.921	Excellent Sampling Adequacy
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity (Chi ²)	1785.342	Significant
Degrees of Freedom (df)	231	–
Significance Level (p-value)	0.000	Less than 0.05 (Significant)

In Table 2, we check if the data is good to use for more analysis. First test is KMO, which should be above 0.6 to be acceptable. Our result is 0.921, which is excellent and shows that the data is suitable for factor analysis. The second test is Bartlett’s test, which checks if the data has relationships between the variables. If the p-value is less than 0.05, we can continue. Our Chi-square value is 1785.342, and $p = 0.000$, so it is significant. This means the items in the questionnaire are related and can be studied together.

Table 3. Correlation between Variables and the Total Questionnaire Score

Variable/Dimension	Pearson’s Correlation (r)	Significance Level (p-value)	Interpretation
Administrative Decentralization	0.781	0.000	Strong positive correlation
Financial Decentralization	0.756	0.000	Strong positive correlation
Institutional Performance	0.839	0.000	Very strong positive correlation
Total Score	1.000	–	Perfect correlation (self)

In Table 3, we see the correlation between each main dimension and the total questionnaire score. Correlation tells us how much two things move together. For administrative decentralization, the correlation is 0.781, and for financial decentralization it is 0.756. Both are strong and positive, meaning as decentralization increases, the total performance is also likely to increase. The institutional performance itself has correlation 0.839 with total score, which is very strong. This

shows that all dimensions are well connected and reflect the total idea of the questionnaire. So, all these results confirm that our tool is good, and the data is ready for deeper analysis.

Research Data Description

Before we show the results in detail, it is important to give short explanation about the data we collect from the field. This helps us to understand who are the people that answer the questionnaire and what their background is. It also gives clear picture about the structure of the sample and how the information was collected. This part includes descriptions of demographic data like gender, age, qualification, and experience. These details help to see if the sample is balanced and if the answers represent real managers in the public departments of Al-Qadisiyyah governorate. The next part explains this information in numbers and percentage.

Table 4. Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (N = 102)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	73	71.6%
	Female	29	28.4%
Age	Under 30	12	11.8%
	30–39	28	27.5%
	40–49	35	34.3%
	50 and above	27	26.4%
Academic Qualification	Diploma	10	9.8%
	Bachelor's Degree	52	51.0%
	Master's Degree	30	29.4%
	Doctorate	10	9.8%
Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	8	7.8%
	5–10 years	24	23.5%
	11–15 years	39	38.2%
	More than 15 years	31	30.4%

The demographic data in Table 4 show important information about the sample of the study. The total number of respondents is 102 managers from public departments in Al-Qadisiyyah governorate. For gender, the table shows that 73 of the respondents are male (71.6%), while only 29 are female (28.4%). This means that most leadership roles in public departments are still held by men, and the number of female managers is much lower, which may reflect the structure of management positions in Iraq's public sector. For age, the largest group is between 40 and 49 years old, with 35 managers (34.3%), followed by 30–39 years with 28 respondents (27.5%). Managers aged 50 and above are 27 (26.4%), and those under 30 are only 12 (11.8%). This result shows that most managers are middle-aged, which is expected because such positions often require experience. This also means that the sample includes people with enough work background to give useful answers about decentralization and performance. The academic qualifications show that more than half of the managers have a bachelor's degree (51.0%), while 29.4% have a master's degree and only 9.8% have a doctorate. Another 9.8% have a diploma. This means most of the managers have a good educational level, which is important for understanding management issues. The presence of postgraduate qualifications (around 39.2%) also shows that many managers are well-educated and can deal with advanced topics like decentralization policy and institutional effectiveness.

For years of experience, the biggest group is those with 11 to 15 years of work, which is 39 respondents (38.2%). This is followed by those with more than 15 years (30.4%), then 5 to 10 years (23.5%), and the smallest group is managers with less than 5 years (7.8%). These results mean that most respondents are experienced and have been working in the system long enough to observe the real impact of decentralization. This gives more credibility to their answers because they are

not new or untrained. the table shows that the sample includes both male and female managers, with a wide age range and different levels of education and experience. The sample is diverse and suitable for analyzing the topic of this study. The strong representation of experienced and educated managers makes the results more reliable.

Demographic Distribution of Respondents

Figure 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (N = 102)

The results from the descriptive statistics in Tables 5, 6, and 7 show how the managers in Al-Qadisiyyah governorate see the situation of decentralization and institutional performance in their departments:

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics – Administrative Decentralization (N = 102)

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Likert Interpretation	Relative Importance (%)
Authority is delegated to lower-level managers effectively.	3.670	0.520	High	73.400
Decision-making is shared across different administrative levels.	3.900	0.480	High	78.000
Employees are encouraged to participate in setting goals.	3.850	0.590	High	77.000
Responsibilities are clearly defined and distributed.	4.000	0.550	High	80.000
There is flexibility in handling administrative procedures.	4.100	0.510	High	82.000
The organization adopts a bottom-up approach in administrative planning.	4.200	0.470	Very High	84.000
Overall Dimension Score	3.953	0.520	High	78.733

In Table 5, the data about administrative decentralization shows that most items received a high level of agreement. The mean values range from 3.670 to 4.200. The lowest was for the item "Authority is delegated to lower-level managers effectively" with mean 3.670, which is still high but maybe some departments don't give full delegation. The highest mean was 4.200 for "The organization adopts a bottom-up approach in administrative planning," which got a very high interpretation with 84% relative importance. This shows that many departments involve lower levels in planning. The overall mean score for this dimension is 3.953, which is high, with 78.733% relative importance. This mean administrative decentralization is applied well in general, but still can improve in some items.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics – Financial Decentralization (N = 102)

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Likert Interpretation	Relative Importance (%)
Local departments have authority to allocate their budgets.	3.800	0.510	High	76.000
Financial decisions are made without waiting for central approval.	3.900	0.470	High	78.000
Revenues are managed and utilized efficiently at the department level.	3.950	0.450	High	79.000
Department managers are involved in budget planning.	4.000	0.490	High	80.000
Resources are allocated based on local priorities.	4.100	0.460	High	82.000
Financial procedures are transparent and documented.	4.200	0.420	Very High	84.000
Overall Dimension Score	3.992	0.467	High	79.833

In Table 6, the financial decentralization also shows strong results. All items have mean between 3.800 and 4.200, and all interpretations are high or very high. The item with highest score is "Financial procedures are transparent and documented" with a mean of 4.200 and 84% relative importance. This means that financial transparency is well applied in many departments. The lowest score is "Local departments have authority to allocate their budgets" with mean 3.800, which still shows good but maybe some departments still need more freedom in budget decisions. The overall score of financial decentralization is 3.992, with 79.833% relative importance. These results show that managers agree that financial decentralization is practiced in a good level, and it help departments to work more effectively.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics – Institutional Performance (N = 102)

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Likert Interpretation	Relative Importance (%)
The institution achieves its strategic goals effectively.	4.100	0.480	High	82.000
Employee productivity has improved in recent years.	4.200	0.460	Very High	84.000
Service delivery meets public expectations.	4.300	0.470	Very High	86.000
Performance evaluation mechanisms are clearly implemented.	4.000	0.500	High	80.000
Feedback from stakeholders is used to improve services.	3.900	0.490	High	78.000
The institution responds quickly to challenges.	3.850	0.520	High	77.000
Employee satisfaction has increased.	3.900	0.530	High	78.000
Innovation and improvement are encouraged.	4.000	0.480	High	80.000
Institutional objectives are reviewed and updated regularly.	3.800	0.500	High	76.000
Resources are managed efficiently.	3.900	0.510	High	78.000
Overall Dimension Score	4.005	0.494	High	80.100

In Table 7, the institutional performance dimension also shows high values. All items have mean between 3.800 and 4.300. The item "Service delivery meets public expectations" scored the highest with a mean of 4.300 and 86% relative importance, which mean the public departments are trying to provide good service. The item "Institutional objectives are reviewed and updated regularly" scored the lowest with mean 3.800, which may mean some departments don't update their goals often. Other items like employee satisfaction, innovation, and feedback also show high means. The overall score for institutional performance is 4.005, which is high, with 80.100% relative importance. This shows that the managers believe their institutions are performing well and meeting their goals, but still have space for more progress in some areas.

Table 8. Multiple Regression Analysis Results

Indicator		Value			
R (Correlation Coefficient)		0.874			
R ² (Coefficient of Determination)		0.764			
Adjusted R ²		0.758			
Standard Error of Estimate		0.215			
Durbin-Watson		1.942			
Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p-value)
Regression	22.814	2	11.407	246.89	0.000
Residual	7.036	99	0.071		
Total	29.850	101			
Predictor Variable	B (Unstandardized)	Std. Error	Beta (Standardized)	t	Sig. (p-value)
Constant	1.032	0.148	–	6.973	0.000
Administrative Decentralization	0.521	0.063	0.604	8.270	0.000
Financial Decentralization	0.378	0.071	0.432	5.324	0.000

Table 8 shows the main results from the regression analysis, which we used to understand how much administrative decentralization and financial decentralization affect institutional performance. First, the R value is 0.874. This means there is a strong connection between decentralization and performance. When R is close to 1, it means the relationship is very strong, and in this case, it clearly shows that the more decentralization is applied, the better the institutional performance becomes.

Then we look at R², which is 0.764. This number tells us how much of the change in institutional performance can be explained by the two types of decentralization together. So here, 76.4% of the change in performance is because of administrative and financial decentralization. This is a very high percentage and shows that these two factors play a big role. The adjusted R² is 0.758, which is very close to R², and this means the model still works well even when adjusting for the number of predictors. The standard error is 0.215, which is a small number and shows that the predicted values from the model are very close to the real values.

The Durbin-Watson value is 1.942. This number checks if there is autocorrelation, which means repeated errors in the data. The ideal number is 2. Since 1.942 is very close to 2, it means there is no problem with autocorrelation, and the model is stable.

The next part of the table talks about the ANOVA results. The F value is 246.89, and the p-value is 0.000. This means the overall model is statistically significant. In simple words, it means the two variables we used (administrative and financial decentralization) do really influence the dependent variable (institutional performance), and the result is not random.

Looking at the coefficients of each variable, the constant is 1.032. This means if there is no decentralization at all, the institutional performance will still be at a basic level of 1.032. Administrative decentralization has an unstandardized B value of 0.521. This means if administrative decentralization increases by one unit, the institutional performance increases by 0.521 units. The standardized beta is 0.604, which means it has a strong effect compared to the other variable. The T value is 8.270, and the p-value is 0.000, so the result is statistically strong.

Financial decentralization has a B value of 0.378. This means it also increases institutional performance, but a little less than administrative decentralization. The beta is 0.432, the t value is 5.324, and the p-value is 0.000. This also means the result is significant.

Table 9. Diagnostic Tests for Model Quality

Diagnostic Test	Value	Interpretation
Multicollinearity (VIF)		
- Administrative Decentralization	1.42	No multicollinearity (VIF < 5)
- Financial Decentralization	1.42	No multicollinearity (VIF < 5)
Tolerance		
- Administrative Decentralization	0.704	Acceptable (Tolerance > 0.1)
- Financial Decentralization	0.704	Acceptable (Tolerance > 0.1)
Durbin-Watson	1.942	No autocorrelation (close to 2)
Normality of Residuals (Kolmogorov-Smirnov)	0.082	$p = 0.200 > 0.05$, residuals are normally distributed
Homoscedasticity (Breusch-Pagan Test)	$\chi^2 = 2.146$	$p = 0.342 > 0.05$, homoscedasticity confirmed
Linearity (Partial Regression Plots)	Visual check	Confirmed linear relationship with dependent variable
Influential Points (Cook's Distance)	Max = 0.034	No influential outliers (below threshold of 1.0)

Table 9 shows that the model is working well. There is no problem between the variables (VIF is 1.42), and tolerance is good (0.704). The errors are normal (Kolmogorov-Smirnov $p = 0.200$), and the data is stable (Breusch-Pagan $p = 0.342$). The line between variables is clear, and no strange values affect the results (Cook's Distance = 0.034). Also, the Durbin-Watson is 1.942, so there is no error repeated. Everything is okay and the model is safe to use. And figure.2 explain this:

Figure 2. Normality of Residuals

Conclusions and Recommendations

The results of this study show that decentralization has a strong and positive effect on how public institutions perform. Both administrative and financial decentralization help managers do their work better. When they have more power to make decisions and control budgets, the institution becomes more active, faster, and more organized. The analysis shows that administrative decentralization has a little stronger effect than financial decentralization, but both are important. The data was reliable, the model passed all tests, and the managers gave clear answers that support the idea of decentralization. Based on these findings, we recommend that public departments in Al-Qadisiyyah and other places should give more authority to local managers. They should be allowed to plan, decide, and manage their own budgets. At the same time, there should be clear rules, training, and a system to follow up their performance. Also, financial transparency and support from higher authorities are needed to make decentralization successful. This can help improve services and make the government work better for the people.

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